

INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE OF LISTED AGRICULTURAL FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14245401>

Abstract: *The study determined the effect of intellectual capital on the corporate performance of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. The specific objective was to examine the effect of human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. The research employs an ex-post facto research design. The population of this study consists of the five (5) listed agricultural firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The research employed secondary data sourced from audited annual reports and accounts of the chosen companies, from 2013 to 2023. To test the hypotheses, the data were subjected to analysis using the pooled Ordinary Least Squares method. The finding revealed that human capital efficiency has a positive significant effect on the return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. Structural capital efficiency has a negative but insignificant effect on the return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria; capital employed efficiency has a positive significant effect on the return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. It was recommended that agricultural firms should consider strategic investments in employee training and development, aiming to enhance overall productivity and consequently improve financial performance.*

Keywords: *Human capital efficiency, Structural capital efficiency and Capital employed efficiency and return on equity*

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a notable shift in the business landscape, with companies increasingly acknowledging the pivotal role that intellectual capital plays in determining their success. Traditionally, the focus had been primarily on tangible assets, such as physical infrastructure and financial resources (Olohunlana, *et al*, 2023; Awwad & Qtaishat, 2023). However, as the business environment evolves and becomes more knowledge-driven, the value of intangible assets, particularly intellectual capital, has become increasingly apparent. Intellectual capital encompasses a broad spectrum of intangible resources, including the expertise and skills of employees, proprietary knowledge, innovative ideas, brand reputation, customer relationships, and organizational culture (Gidado, *et al*, 2023; Rufus *et al*,

2022). These intangible assets collectively contribute to an organization's competitive advantage and differentiation in the market. Recognizing the significance of intellectual capital, forward-thinking businesses have started placing greater emphasis on nurturing and leveraging these intangible resources to drive growth, innovation, and profitability (Otuya, *et al* 2023).

The role of intellectual capital in achieving competitiveness has garnered significant attention due to technological advancements, globalization, and the rise of knowledge-based economies (Abba, *et al* 2023). Intellectual capital has often been recognized as a crucial factor influencing the productivity and strategic competitiveness of firms. Intellectual capital refers to a collection of intellectual material, knowledge, experience, property, and information that contributes to creating value within an organization (Putri, *et al* 2023; Uagbale-Ekatak & Ofurum, 2022). It represents the wealth of knowledge that a company utilizes in its business operations to generate value. Studies have established that intellectual capital is an intangible asset that can influence a firm's earnings potential and absorptive capacity, making it increasingly regarded as a paramount resource for organizations (Ashraf, Sadiq, Ferreira & Almeida, 2023). In Nigeria, the recognition of intellectual capital's importance is evident in many annual reports and accounts, where the phrase "our greatest assets are our people" frequently appears (Major & Biragbara, 2023). This growing acknowledgment of intellectual capital is based on the belief that people hold as much value as other organizational resources. Over the years, the significance of intellectual capital has significantly increased, and it is now considered a crucial tool for achieving sustainable competitive advantage (Edet, *et al*, 2023). People are the most influential factor in value creation, as tangible assets can only add value when human beings effectively utilize them. Intellectual capital's dominance is a characteristic of emerging economies driven by global competition; and the valuation of intellectual capital within organizations should be based on its performance, further emphasizing its critical role in organizational success (Habib & Dalwai, 2023).

The assessment of intellectual capital efficiency involves determining whether the efforts made in developing intellectual capital contribute to achieving objectives or improving specific outcomes, such as reducing worker absences and turnover, enhancing work efficiency, and increasing productivity (Nguyen, 2023; Chukwuekwu, 2023). At the organizational level, efficiency evaluation provides insights into the company's ability to generate profits from its available resources and ensure future liquidity. This efficiency results from optimizing time, labor, and process costs (Salman, 2023). The effective utilization of human resources plays a crucial role in determining an organization's strength, with intellectual capital efficiency revolving around maximizing productivity from human assets while minimizing costs (Tonye & Oruh, 2022).

In the knowledge-based economy, where information and ideas hold immense power, intellectual capital serves as a critical driver of corporate performance (Abuaddous, *et al*, 2023). Companies that effectively harness their employees' expertise, foster a culture of learning and knowledge sharing, and

invest in research and development are better positioned to thrive in dynamic and competitive markets. Intellectual capital also plays a vital role in enhancing decision-making processes, enabling companies to make strategic choices backed by valuable insights and informed analyses (Edet, *et al*, 2023).

As the business world becomes increasingly interconnected and digitalized, intellectual capital has emerged as a key differentiator, allowing companies to innovate, adapt, and stay relevant amidst rapid technological advancements and evolving customer preferences. In this context, the effective management and utilization of intellectual capital have become imperative for sustained success and resilience in a rapidly changing business landscape.

Therefore, the growing recognition of the significance of intellectual capital reflects a paradigm shift in how businesses perceive and leverage their assets. By appreciating the inherent value of knowledge, expertise, and intangible resources, companies are better equipped to optimize their corporate performance, achieve competitive advantage, and build a solid foundation for long-term growth and prosperity. As organizations continue to navigate the complexities of the modern business environment, the effective management and harnessing of intellectual capital will remain central to unlocking new opportunities and driving success in the ever-evolving corporate landscape (Misdar, 2023). A failure to fully harness intellectual capital might lead to reduced innovation, decreased productivity, and inefficient decision-making processes. Additionally, these organizations might struggle to attract and retain top talent, as employees may seek opportunities in firms that prioritize and invest in their professional development (Ashraf, *et al*, 2023). Ultimately, the limited integration of intellectual capital into corporate strategies could hinder the overall performance of Nigerian firms, impacting their ability to thrive in the dynamic and competitive business environment. Existing studies in Nigeria have not included the evidence from 2022 accounting period with respect to agricultural sector of the Nigerian Exchange Group. Besides, there is a sectorial gap, none of the prior studies carried out research on this nature using agricultural sector in Nigeria. This study addresses this gap in literature; the study consequently, determines the effect of intellectual capital on the corporate performance of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To examine the effect of human capital efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the effect of structural capital efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.
3. To determine the effect of capital employed efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Intellectual Capital

The initial definition of intellectual capital is attributed to Thomas Stewart, a pioneer of the concept. In 1991, in an article titled "Brain Power - How Intellectual Capital is Becoming America's Most Valuable Asset," Stewart defined intellectual capital as the collective knowledge within a company that provides it with a competitive advantage in the market over other firms (Lee & Shek, 2022). This knowledge effectively transforms raw materials and adds value to them. Thus, any knowledge base used for wealth creation is referred to as intellectual capital (Olohunlana *et al*, 2023). The concept of intellectual capital delves into the intangible yet immensely valuable assets that go beyond traditional financial measures (Nguyen, 2023). It encompasses the wealth of knowledge, skills, relationships, and organizational processes that contribute to a company's ability to innovate, compete, and ultimately succeed in the dynamic business landscape (Chukwuekwu, 2023). At its core, intellectual capital is about leveraging what a company knows and how it operates to create a distinct advantage.

Thomas Stewart's foundational definition captures this essence by highlighting that intellectual capital encompasses the collective wisdom embedded in the minds of a company's employees (Çevik & Arslan, 2022). This knowledge is not limited to facts and figures but extends to insights, best practices, problem-solving approaches, and other intangible assets that can't be easily quantified (Edet, *et al* 2023). Intellectual capital encompasses the non-physical sources of added value for a firm, including human capital (such as skills, training, and experience), relational capital (including customer and stakeholder relationships, agreements, and brands), and structural capital (such as company culture, systems, working environment, and intangible rights) (Putri, *et al* 2023).

Intellectual capital encompasses or represents the economic value of human, relational, and structural capital, all of which are intangible assets for a firm (Otuya, *et al* 2023). Intellectual capital refers to a complex organizational process involving knowledge management, best practice transfer, and organizational learning. This process transforms employees' skills, knowledge, and expertise into valuable assets crucial for organizational performance. In more specific terms, intellectual capital constitutes the intangible value derived from employee knowledge, skills, business training, and ideas – assets that are not listed in the financial position statement (Chukwuekwu, 2023).

The economic value and success of modern firms rely not only on their manufactured products but also on their intangible assets, which enhance employees' knowledge base for improved productivity and efficiency (Tonye & Oruh, 2022). Intellectual capital encompasses external factors (like brand and reputation) and internal factors (such as skills and competencies), dynamically interlinked intangible assets that enable corporations to leverage tangible assets, financial resources, and human capital to create value (Abba *et al*, 2023).

Human Capital Efficiency

Human capital efficiency compresses a collection of factors that not only encompass the knowledge and skills possessed by employees but also extend to their intrinsic qualities and how these attributes

contribute to the overall functioning of an organization (Major & Biragbara, 2023). Human capital efficiency emphasizes the idea that employees are not just cogs in the machine but rather the driving force behind a company's growth and development (Al-Delawi, *et al* 2023). This intellectual capital category includes not only technical skills but also intangible qualities like creativity, adaptability, and problem-solving abilities (Abba, *et al* 2023). These attributes contribute to the employees' ability to innovate, find novel solutions, and adapt to changing circumstances – all of which are indispensable in today's fast-paced business environment.

Moreover, human capital efficiency is a multi-dimensional concept that incorporates various aspects of an employee's background and disposition (Salman, 2023). The significance of human capital efficiency within the broader realm of intellectual capital is profound since human capital is not only a component but the linchpin of intellectual capital (Al-Delawi, *et al* 2023). This assertion is grounded in the understanding that a skilled, motivated, and innovative workforce is the bedrock upon which competitive advantage and groundbreaking innovations are built.

Structural Capital Efficiency

Structural capital efficiency encompasses a diverse spectrum of elements that collectively form the foundation upon which a company's intellectual prowess is built (Salman, 2023). This facet of intellectual capital embraces an array of crucial components – technologies, data repositories, inventive creations, published materials, organizational culture, strategic frameworks, structural setups, and operational systems (Abuaddous, *et al*, 2023). In essence, it is the intricate tapestry of procedures, methods, and activities that a company strategically assembles.

The significance of structural capital efficiency goes beyond its mere existence within an organization. It significantly influences the innovation process and directly contributes to the formation of innovative capital – the lifeblood of forward-looking enterprises (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023). The incorporation of advanced technologies and methodologies into operational processes, systems, and structures enhances a company's ability to not only produce goods but also effectively market and distribute them. Structural capital efficiency comprises the efficiency of vital organizational processes, the accessibility and management of data through databases, the safeguarding of trademarks, the functionality of information systems, and even the intangible aspects of corporate culture (Abba, *et al* 2023). In simpler terms, structural capital encapsulates the legacy that remains embedded within a company even when the workforce departs at the end of the day.

Capital Employed Efficiency

Capital employed refers to the comprehensive sum of resources strategically deployed within a firm's fixed and current assets (Tonye & Oruh, 2022). It encompasses the amalgamation of equity capital and noncurrent liabilities – a composite of funding sources that sustains the company's operations. In simpler terms, capital employed encapsulates the aggregate value of fixed assets and working capital.

However, the mere presence of capital employed doesn't tell the full story – it's the efficiency with which these resources are utilized that truly matters. Capital employed efficiency entails all the intricacies of resource utilization within a firm's production and business activities (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023).

Capital employed efficiency emerges as a strategic avenue for this optimization. It's akin to a performance metric that gauges the organization's ability to convert financial inputs into valuable outputs. This dimension of intellectual capital is not just about the numbers; it reflects the company's acumen in efficient resource allocation, process optimization, and value creation (Otuya, *et al* 2023). Thus, capital employed efficiency is a strategic lever that companies can pull to achieve their broader financial objectives (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023). It embodies the intelligent allocation of resources, operational optimization, and value creation – all of which contribute to the enhancement of the firm's overall competitiveness and long-term sustainability.

Corporate Performance

Corporate performance pertains to the utilization of a company's resources within its core operations to generate revenue effectively (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023). Alternatively, it encompasses the achievement of specific business objectives, evaluated against predefined benchmarks, targets, and expenditures. Corporate performance reflects the degree to which a company attains its strategic goals and objectives with optimal resource employment (Uagbale-Ekatakah & Ofurum, 2022). Corporate performance refers to the measure of the comprehensive competitiveness of an economic entity. It provides insights into the level of accomplishment regarding a firm's strategic aims (Habib & Dalwai, 2023). Corporate performance involves a holistic assessment of how effectively a firm executes its policies and operations to fulfill its predefined objectives (Gidado, *et al* 2023). This encompasses a quantifiable outcome that showcases the extent of goal attainment. Through a meticulously structured evaluation of corporate performance, managers gain the capability to assess the financial prosperity, health, and sustainability of the firm. This accentuates that the concept of corporate performance extends beyond it is mere face value, incorporating dimensions such as firm productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, and more, beyond the conventional focus on financial performance often found in corporate literature.

Return on Assets (ROA)

ROA assesses how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate earnings. For manufacturing firms, this is crucial since they often have significant investments in machinery and inventory. By optimizing production processes and managing asset utilization, companies can improve their ROA, demonstrating better financial performance. The ROA provides insight into a business's performance by indicating the rate at which capital expenditures generate profit. Due to the audit committees' significant interest influence on how a firm produces wealth, the return on assets (ROA) statistic is frequently used.

Empirical Review

Nguyen (2023) evaluated the effect of intellectual capital on firm financial performance in the service sector of Vietnam from 2005–2014. Using two-step system GMM model, the results express that human capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency have positive effect on firm performance whereas the impact of structural capital efficiency was inconsistent, depending on the knowledge intensity levels and the types of service activities. Chukwuekwu (2023) examined the influence of intellectual capital on growth of firms listed in Nigerian stock Exchange. A sample size of 10 listed consumer goods firms over a period of ten years (2011-2020) was used as sample size for this study. Regression analysis techniques were used to investigate the effect of Intellectual Capital and its components on business sustainability growth. Results from the analyses revealed that Physical Capital, Human Capital, Structural Capital and Relational Capital exert significant positive effect in predicting corporate sustainable growth. Putri, *et al* (2023) analyzed the effect of Intellectual Capital on financial performance and firm value of Indonesian automotive industry. The population in this study were automotive companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2014-2021. To test the hypothesis, the study used Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis. The results of the hypothesis test showed that intellectual Capital has a positive and significant effect on financial performance. Otuya, *et al* (2023) investigated how intellectual capital efficiency contributes to creating shareholders' wealth in Nigeria from 2011 to 2022. The study utilized the VAIC model to estimate intellectual capital, followed by descriptive statistics and diagnostic tests before regression analysis. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between values added intellectual coefficient (VAIC), as a gauge of intellectual capital, and shareholders' wealth. Abba, Hamidu, *et al* (2023) ascertained the impact of intellectual capital on the enterprise value of listed technical businesses in Nigeria. For the period from 2012 to 2020, a working population of seven out of nine enterprises was chosen. The study's findings, which were determined using correlation and multiple regression analysis, indicate that Intellectual Capital has a negative and significant impact on enterprise value. Olohunlana, *et al* (2023) determined the extent of intellectual capital efficiency in listed commercial banks in Nigeria and the factors influencing its effective utilization. Utilizing data envelopment analysis (DEA) on annual financial reports from 2013 to 2019, the study assesses intellectual capital efficiency for these banks. Subsequently, employing Tobit regression, the research analyzes the influence of firm-specific factors on intellectual capital efficiency. Results reveal that only 8.33% of the surveyed Nigerian commercial banks effectively optimize their intellectual capital, while 91.67% operate inefficiently. Habib and Dalwai (2023) explored the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on the firm performance of the GCC industrial sector. The data were gathered from Standard & Poor's database from 2015 to 2019. The results indicate that most firms do not employ their intellectual capital investments well and need

improvement actions to achieve the best practices. The regression model results reveal that intellectual capital efficiency significantly and positively influences firms' performance. Abuaddous, *et al* (2023) examined the impact of intellectual capital (human capital, structural capital and employed capital) on the financial performance of listed insurance companies in the Amman Stock Exchange. The study population consists of 21 insurance companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange in Jordan during the period of 2011-2020. The results of the multiple regression analysis found that human capital and capital employed have significant positive effect on return on equity whereas structural capital does not. Sonali and Kaushala (2023) examined the impact of Intellectual Capital on consumer staples firm performance in Colombia. Data were collected from a sample of 25 Consumer Staple sector companies listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange for the period from 2012 to 2020 and EViews was used for the panel data regression analysis to validate the hypothesis. This study found that Human Capital and Capital Employed have a significant positive impact on firm performance in the consumer staples sector. However, Structural Capital has no significant impact on the firm performance. Misdar (2023) analyzed the influence of intellectual capital on financial performance of banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2019-2021. The data used in this study is secondary data obtained from the financial statements of banking companies. Linear Regression Test was used in testing the study's hypotheses which revealed that human capital, structural capital, and relational capital positively affect the financial performance (FP) of firms. Tonye and Oruh (2022) investigated the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on economic value of listed consumer firms in Nigeria for the period of 2016-2020. The result of the regression analysis showed that Human capital efficiency and Structural capital efficiency has positive and significant impact on economic value (ROA). However, Capital employed efficiency shows negative and non-significant effect on economic value in Nigeria. Rufus, Festus and Dada (2022) examined the effect of intellectual capital on organisational performance of financial companies quoted in Nigeria. The study adopted *Ex-Post Facto* research design. The audited financial statements from 2010 to 2019 validated by the external auditors' report were the data source. Descriptive and inferential statistics using regression analyses were employed. The study found that human capital efficiency and structural capital efficiency has a non-significant positive effect on organizational performance whereas capital employed efficiency has a significant positive effect on firm performance.

Methodology

The research employs an ex-post facto research design, specifically utilizing the casual-comparative method. Ex-post facto research involves a study where the researcher works with independent variables that cannot be manipulated during the research process.

Population and Sample Size of the Study

The population of the study consists of the five agricultural firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The study covered ten years annual reports and accounts of these companies from 2013 to 2023. The firms are Ellah Lakes Plc, Ftn Cocoa Processors Plc Livestock Feeds Plc, Okomu Oil Palm Plc and Presco Plc. The researcher used all the five agricultural firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group for the sample size

Method of Data Collection

The research employs secondary data sourced from audited annual reports and accounts of the chosen companies. The data is extracted from the Statement of Financial Position and the Statement of Profit or Loss and Comprehensive Income. This dataset spans duration of eleven years, from 2013 to 2023. Annual reports and accounts are considered reputable and dependable sources as they bear the endorsement of the management, gain approval from the Security and Exchange Commission (SEC), and undergo external audit scrutiny.

Model Specification

The study adapted the model by Tonye and Oruh (2022)

$$EVA = a_0 + a_1 HCE_{it} + b_2 SCE_{it} + b_3 CEE_{it} + u$$

Where;

A₀ = constant

EVA = Economic Value (ROA)

HCE = Human capital efficiency

SCE = Structural capital efficiency

CEE = Capital employed efficiency

The model above was modified to produce the specific model suitable for the study.

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HCE_{it} + \beta_2 SCE_{it} + \beta_3 CEE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots i$$

Where:

ROA is Return on Asset, calculated as earnings after-tax/total asset

HCE is Human Capital Efficiency, which is calculated as (Value Added)/(Human Capital)

SCE is Structural Capital Efficiency, which is calculated as (Structural Capital)/(Value Added)

CCE is Capital Employed Efficiency, which is calculated as (Value Added)/(Capital Employed)

β₁₋₃ represents the regression coefficient;

ε represents the error term;

i represents individual firms and t represents the time/year.

Method of Data Analysis

The analysis of data for this research based on the data collected from publications of the Nigerian exchange Group and the annual reports of the quoted companies. Both the dependent and independent variables were computed from the data gotten from the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2013 to 2023.

Descriptive statistics employed to summarily describe the mean, median, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness of the study variables. Inferential statistics will also be utilized with the aid of E-Views 9 using:

- i. Coefficient of correlation: which is a good measure of relationship between two variables that tell us about the strength of relationship and the direction of the relationship as well?
- ii. Multiple regressions analysis: Regression analysis predicts the value the dependent variable based on the value of the independent variable and explains the impact or effect of changes in the values of the variables.

Decision Rule

Accept the alternative hypothesis, if the Probability value (P-value) of the test is less than 0.05 (5%). Otherwise reject.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	ROA	HCE	SCE	CEE
Mean	0.076364	1.483636	0.296364	0.417273
Median	0.060000	1.490000	0.330000	0.440000
Maximum	0.250000	2.450000	0.590000	0.530000
Minimum	-0.030000	0.930000	0.010000	0.300000
Std. Dev.	0.072683	0.391608	0.156541	0.071633
Skewness	1.115822	0.962255	-0.178810	-0.361344
Kurtosis	3.803077	4.120435	2.660200	1.962661
Jarque-Bera	12.89100	11.36463	0.557692	3.662884
Probability	0.001588	0.003406	0.756656	0.160182
Sum	4.200000	81.60000	16.30000	22.95000
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.285273	8.281273	1.323273	0.277091
Observations	55	55	55	55

Source: E-View output, 2024

Interpretation of Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics in table 1 revealed that the return on assets of the sampled companies is 0.076; the maximum of 0.250 with a minimum of -0.030 with a standard deviation of 0.073. The average human capital efficiency (HCE) from the sampled observations is 1.484; standard deviation of 0.392; a maximum observation of 2.450 with a minimum value of 1.930. The mean value of structural capital efficiency (SCE) stood at 0.296, a standard deviation of 0.157; maximum observation of 0.590 with a minimum value of 0.010. The mean of capital employed efficiency (CEE) is at the average of 0.417; standard deviation of 0.072; a maximum observation of 0.530 with a minimum value of 0.300.

Skewness is the measure of how much the probability distribution of a random variable deviates from the normal distribution. Table 1 delineates that the probability distribution for ROA (0.002); HCE (0.003); SCE (0.757) and CEE (0.160) are positively skewed distribution.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	ROA	HCE	SCE	CEE
ROE	1			
HCE	0.70671	1		
SCE	0.59207	0.95450	1	
CEE	0.28083	0.30073	0.40866	1

Source: E-Views 9.0 Correlation Output, 2024

The Pearson Correlation Matrix in table 2 shows the existence of a positive relationship between HCE, SCE, CEE and ROA at a coefficient value of 0.706, 0.592 and 0.281.

Test of Hypotheses

In other to examine the impact relationships between the dependent variable debt and the independent variables (HCE, SCE and CEE) and to also test our formulated hypotheses, we used a pooled multiple regression analysis since the data had both time series (2013-2023) and cross sectional properties (Nigerian agricultural firms). The pooled interaction based multiple regression results are presented and discussed in Table 3 below.

Table 3: OLS Regression Result

Dependent Variable: ROE

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 10/20/24 Time: 23:06

Sample: 2013 2023

Periods included: 11

Cross-sections included: 5

Total panel (balanced) observations: 55

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.359111	0.067403	-5.327851	0.0000
HCE	0.340917	0.056870	5.994686	0.0000
SCE	-0.585374	0.148662	-3.937615	0.0003
CEE	0.247229	0.101582	2.433789	0.0185
R-squared	0.620073	Mean dependent var		0.076364
Adjusted R-squared	0.597724	S.D. dependent var		0.072683
S.E. of regression	0.046099	Akaike info criterion		-3.246088
Sum squared resid	0.108383	Schwarz criterion		-3.100100
Log likelihood	93.26741	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.189633

F-statistic	27.74545	Durbin-Watson stat	1.544329
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: E-Views 9.0 Correlation Output, 2024

Interpretation of Regression Result

In table 3, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.62) and (0.60) respectively. The indicates that all the independent variables jointly explain about 60% of the systematic variations in debt of our samples firms over the ten years periods (2013-2023). Table 3 revealed an adjusted R² value of 0.60. The adjusted R², which represents the coefficient of multiple determinations imply that 60% of the total variation in the dependent variable (debt) of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria is jointly explained by the explanatory variables (HCE, SCE, and CEE). The adjusted R² of 60% did not constitute a problem to the study because the F- statistics value of 27.74545 with an associated Prob.>F = 0.000 indicates that the model is fit to explain the relationship expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined and used. The value of adjusted R² of 60% also shows that 40% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by other factors not captured in the study model.

Test of Autocorrelation: using Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics which we obtained from our regression result in table 3, it is observed that DW statistics is 1.544 and an Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion which are -3.246 and -3.100 respectively also further confirms that our model is well specified. In addition to the above, the specific findings from each explanatory variable are provided as follows:

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Human capital efficiency does not significantly affect return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria

Table 3 indicates that human capital efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect on return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.340917 with p-value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Decision

Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%)., this study upholds that human capital efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect return on assets of agricultural firms in Nigeria Thus, null hypothesis is Rejected and alternative hypothesis Accepted.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Structural capital efficiency does not significantly affect return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Table 3 indicates that structural capital efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect on return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of -0.585374 with p-value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), this study upholds that structural capital efficiency of the firm has a negative significant effect on return on assets of agricultural firms in Nigeria. Thus, null hypothesis is Rejected and alternative hypothesis Accepted.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Capital employed efficiency does not significantly affect return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Table 3 indicates that capital employed efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect on return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.247229 with p-value of 0.019 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), this study upholds that capital employed efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect on return on equity of agricultural firms in Nigeria. Thus, null hypothesis is Rejected and alternative hypothesis Accepted.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study determined the effect of intellectual capital on the corporate performance of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria, using human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency as the independent variables, while return on assets represent the dependent variable. The research employs an ex-post facto research design. The population of this study consists of the five (5) listed agricultural firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Companies that recognizes the paramount importance of intellectual capital and strategically integrate it into their corporate strategies actively invest in developing and nurturing intellectual capital through employee training and development programs, fostering a knowledge-sharing culture, and promoting innovation and creativity.

The negative impact on ROA highlights the critical role of skilled, motivated, and well-managed human resources in the consumer goods sector. In an environment where innovation and adaptability are key, shortcomings in human capital management can lead to increased costs, reduced productivity, and ultimately, a diminished ROA. The negative effect on ROA underscores the importance of optimizing organizational structures, processes, and technologies. Firms that fail to adapt to evolving market dynamics and technological advancements may face increased operational costs, reduced competitiveness, and, consequently, a lower return on assets. The positive correlation with return on assets emphasizes the significance of prudent financial management and optimal capital allocation. Firms that strategically deploy their overall capital, balancing debt and equity, and investing in high-return projects, are more likely to experience higher profitability and, in turn, a positive impact on ROA.

Therefore, addressing challenges in human capital and structural capital becomes integral to achieving sustained growth and profitability in the competitive agricultural sector.

Recommendations

1. Agricultural firms should consider strategic investments in employee training and development, aiming to enhance overall productivity and consequently improve financial performance.
2. Managers of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria should prioritize streamlining processes, improving intellectual property management, and optimizing supply chain operations. By addressing these structural challenges, firms can work towards improving financial outcomes and maintaining a competitive edge in the market.
3. Recognizing the positive correlation between capital employed efficiency and ROA encourages agricultural firms in Nigeria to focus on optimizing asset utilization, managing debt levels prudently, and making strategic investment decisions to enhance overall financial performance.

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Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2837-1070

Impact Factor: 6.65

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

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